

“What are my options”-concept

Referred to as: [Watmagweltaijdenscrisis.nl](https://www.watmagweltaijdenscrisis.nl)

A collaboration between VeiligheidsRegio Rotterdam - Rijnmond & Tilburg University

Concept note

Authors:

Nikki van Emmerloot (VR-RR)
Nicole van Batenburg (VR-RR)
Kenny Meesters (TiU)

Table of content

Table of content	1
Preface	3
Rationale & Motivation	4
COVID Fatigue & increasing infections	4
Information to empower citizens	5
State of the art	5
Challenges & developments	6
Position in organization	6
Concept	7
Intended outcomes	7
Results	7
Deliverables	7
Impact	8
Next steps & Future developments	8
Community & Ecosystem	8
Development	8
Dissemination	8
Research	9
Use of this concept and documents	9

Disclaimer: This document is publicly available and covered under the [CC-BY 4.0](#) license. You are free to share this material in any medium or format. You can also adapt or build on the ideas provided here, even commercially. Provided that you give appropriate credit to the authors in your project: Nikki van Emmerloot, Nicole van Batenburg, Kenny Meesters. If you like to know more [contact us!](#)

Preface

During the global COVID-19 pandemic government agencies around the globe have introduced measures to stop the spread of the virus. Many of the measures limited the exposure of people to others, and relate to maintaining (physical) distance. This has resulted in reduced availability and access to services and social contacts. As the pandemic continues, the effects of the resulting social distance become increasingly noticeable in our societies and communities. Especially around the holidays and other special events that normally would be opportunities to connect. Combined with the long duration of these measures, people are struggling to maintain distance, adhere to the measures and follow the guidelines. People are looking for ways to make social connections, and even with the best intentions, it can be hard to follow the rules.

Lucky, information and communication technologies (ICTs), creative thinking and (digital) communities have led to creative ideas to stay engaged and facilitate social contacts. In order to not only remind people of the measures and their importance, it is also important to share information about possibilities. In other words, an additional narrative not on restrictions but possibilities. At the same time, people may suffer from an information overload, and need to apply efforts to come up with suitable alternatives. Using modern technologies relevant suggestions can be tailored to the context of the user. We introduce this concept note and the related prototype therefore to demonstrate two principles:

1. Introducing an additional narrative from restrictions to possibilities. And therefore creating an extra incentive for the public to act in accordance with the measures.
2. Tailoring the information to the user-specific context. Thus reducing the cognitive load for people to identify and assess possibilities for undertaking activities.

We encourage you to take these concepts and design documents and develop your own implementations. We invite you to share your ideas, projects and findings with us. At the same time, if you have any questions, suggestions or feedback it would be most welcome.

[Nikki van Emmerloot](#), Safety Region Rotterdam Rijnmond

[Nicole van Batenburg](#), Safety Region Rotterdam Rijnmond

[Kenny Meesters](#), Lecturer Information Management, Tilburg University

Rationale & Motivation

The inspiration for this concept came from a variety of sources. First of all, newspapers report on socio-economic topics that emphasize the impact of the current COVID-19 crisis. Several news articles illustrated the need for a perspective to reduce the anxiety of citizens during the pandemic. Several of the Dutch news articles that illustrate this need for perspective in the COVID-19 are:

- “Het coronavirus omarmen? Dan komen we in een catastrofe terecht”.
Trouw (2020), Retrieved: December 9, 2020, from: <https://www.trouw.nl/nieuws/het-coronavirus-omarmen-dan-komen-we-in-een-catastrofe-terecht-bf02f3707/>
- “Het virus heeft geen provinciegrenzen uit z'n hoofd geleerd”
NRC (2020). Retrieved: December 9, 2020, from: <https://www.nrc.nl/nieuws/2020/11/16/het-virus-heeft-geen-provinciegrenzen-uit-zn-hoofd-geleerd-a4020253>
- “Collectieve angst en de coronapandemie.”
University of Amsterdam (2020) Retrieved: December 9, 2020, from: <https://www.uva.nl/shared-content/faculiteiten/nl/faculteit-der-maatschappij-en-gedragwetenschappen/nieuws/2020/12/collectieve-angst-en-de-coronapandemie.html>
- “Do we learn from a crisis?”
Tilburg University (2020) Retrieved December, 2020 from <https://www.tilburguniversity.edu/magazine/do-we-learn-crisis>
- “Laat met apps zien wat wel kan in coronatijd.”,
Volkskrant (2020). Retrieved, December 9, 2020: <https://www.volkskrant.nl/columns-opinie/laat-met-apps-zien-wat-de-burger-wel-kan-doen-in-coronatijd-bf3bacabd/>

Secondly, there are the press conferences by the cabinet that inform the residents of the Netherlands about the measures necessary to control the Coronavirus. It is notable that these press conferences are solely about the current status of the healthcare system and activities that people can't execute anymore (or not without major adjustments). The narrative and communication is mainly focussed on the repressive crisis management and measures that have to be followed to prevent the virus spread.

COVID Fatigue & increasing infections

Compounding the difficulties in following the measures is the so-called 'COVID-fatigue' (corona-moeheid). The continued crisis with limited outlook and certainties, and even increasing numbers (second wave) along with continuous warnings results in a certain wear in the communication. As certain activities are still not possible, the resolve of the communities weakens. For example, Google Mobility numbers show that people are more on the road compared to the first COVID-19 wave. In fact there is a slow increase in 'official warnings' of government officials who observe and coach the residents of Rotterdam- Rijnmond.

Addendum Dec 14th: The increase in COVID-19 cases isn't declining and indicates that the second wave may take longer to resolve as expected. Therefore the Dutch government announced extra measures (a lockdown) in order to flatten the curve over the holiday period (December 15th 2020 - January 18th 2021). However, a critical opinion is that the public is increasingly struggling to obey these measures. This point of view may occur from the desire to continue the daily life as much as possible and the need for social interactions.

However finding solutions and possibilities require a mental effort of citizens. People have to first identify possibilities, determine if these suit their specific (social) needs, determine if these are allowed within the current measures and how to best implement the idea. This cognitive actions however are not aligned with the information and communication provided by the government agencies, which only focus on the last part (the measures). This constant adaption and evaluation process increases the cognitive load and further adds to the covid-fatigue and reduced motivation to act in accordance with the necessary measures.

Information to empower citizens

Due to many sources of information and subjects, people are suffering from an information overload. The process of receiving new information and translating this to your own personal life is difficult and is transcending their cognitive load. All that new information is constantly changing and evolving, and indicates that residents and governmental agencies have to have a high level of adaptive capacity. Due to this constantly changing environment of information, it is hard to stay focused on the topic. Society tends to move their attention away to other topics that are more related to their daily life and that do not exceed their cognitive load. For example, ringing an alarm in the morning is effective because it grabs our attention and has a clear goal (e.g. waking up in the morning). If this alarm rings randomly at any time it lacks a clear goal and our attention tends to move away because we have no reason to think that the alarm is important.

Nonetheless, people actively seek out information that allows them to undertake certain activities while following the rules and minimizing the risk of spreading the Coronavirus. To reduce the cognitive load we aim to help people find *actionable* and *relevant* tailored to their information need. This concept anticipates this information need and defines a possibility to provide and improve the information offered. Specifically how certain activities *can* be undertaken in COVID-19 times considering the measures and user-context.

Instead of ringing the alarm, it may be more effective to decrease the effort of receiving and translating the information offer and focus on providing perspective to translate information into individuals' daily lives. Transform the focus on what isn't possible into what is possible despite the current COVID-19 situation. Focus on guiding and coaching individuals to learn to dance with the crisis. For more information:

- Dutch: '[Laat met apps zien wat de burger wel kan doen in Coronatijd](#)' Volkskrant (2020)
- English: '[Show people what is still possible despite the corona rules](#)' at Tilburg University (2020)

State of the art

Several initiatives are already up and running to provide perspective and guidance in times of uncertainty and crisis. For example, www.overstroomik.nl, www.denhaagtegenecorona.nl or www.spotrotterdam.nl are platforms that tailor the delivered information to the local context of the user.

Besides these (non)commercial initiatives, communities, organizations and individual citizens initiated events and ideas throughout the pandemic to provide alternatives, new options and redesign of activities and interactions. For example, "bear hunts" were organized in which people placed a teddy bear in front of their windows and families and kids tried to count as many bears as possible in their own neighborhood. This indicates that residents, and society in general, are seeking to find alternatives to provide activities and social engagement in the current COVID-19 situation while at the same time ensuring the measures are followed.

© Maai Ke (Facebook)

The current focus point in many policies of government agencies and crisis management organizations is to guide and coach residents. Nevertheless there is a strong focus on the measures and restrictions. In other words: 'what is prohibited'. Furthermore, there are campaigns who appeal to all the incentives for people to follow the rules. Especially with the upcoming holidays and the changed (increased) restrictions, the messaging has a strong focus on the measures and the importance of following them. With this concept we aim to supplement this communication by connecting social activities, measures, and contextual information needs of citizens. In short this concept tries to provide people perspective to continue their daily lives without feeling contained and/or restricted.

Challenges & developments

The challenge this concept acts upon is that society seeks operational strategies in which residents receive perspective to continue their daily lives without feeling restricted and contained by the current situation.

	Potential (what we want to achieve)	Barriers (what horder do we experience when achieving our potential)	Success factors (what actions do we take to overcome the barriers)
Internal	We are the first governmental institution that provides a 'positive' guideline based on the COVID-19 rules instead of impose strong discouraging orders	It might be a too progressive, out-of-the-box way of communication that clashes with the traditional way of acting during a humanitarian crisis	In order to overcome the barriers, we work with the design-thinking method to break it down into small parts. In this way, our method will become more understandable for VRR employees
External	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) A more positive attitude towards the government, because we make information more applicable and relevant for civilians. (2) An increase of political trust by dutch civilians, who are getting tired of the 'lack of perspective' way of communication by politicians (3) It narrows the gap between civilians and 'elitarian' institutions because we ask people to deliver ideas (4) Creates a shift from a negative, forcing, and demanding tone of voice towards a more positive, helpful, and 'thinking along' tone of voice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Control and regulation because there's a lot at stake (2) Conflict of interest (3) It might be a too progressive, out-of-the-box way of communication 	The pilot version will be strictly regulated by our team, but take civilians' ideas into account. By doing so, we will 1) grow along with the fast-growing and changing society and 2) giving civilians the feeling of being heard since they can relate to the positive guidelines we offer

Position in organization

The following diagram shows the position of this concept, referred to as Platform X, compared to stakeholders. The platform is based on three disciplines, namely: Scenario's, Information Management and Crisis Communication. It serves as an additional service parallel to official measures for containing a crisis. Lastly, it serves residents affected by the crisis. In this case, referred to as residents of the Safety Region Rotterdam Rijnmond.

Concept

The current COVID-19 situation includes an impact on the healthcare system but also on the social-economic environment of individuals. Many ideas, to relieve this impact, are developed by all sorts of organizations and individuals. The objective is to bundle these ideas and make them available through a directory. This directory would be enhanced with (intelligent) filters to match the user-specific context and present relevant ideas. As a result the users may get inspired with new ideas which will lead to new input on the platform.

Intended outcomes

Through this concept the aim is to achieve the following:

1. Improve the **factor trust** in governmental agencies by providing solutions that contribute to an individual's lives. Supplementing the existing crisis communication with more actionable information related to the information needs of the public.
2. Increase the **willingness of civilians** to follow the COVID-19 restrictions, by offering alternative ideas and perspectives. Reducing the cognitive load to identify own alternatives and reducing the risk of people to either follow incorrect advice or not at all.
3. Developing a **working prototype** to identify, design and demonstrate technical, commutative and organizational challenges. Through rapid-prototyping identify the potential of information and communication technologies to offer solutions to these challenges.
4. Mobilize existing **knowledge and networks** to create, develop and disseminate viable alternatives to social activities and life-events. Provide a platform to connect idea providers and the public need for suitable inspiration and alternatives.

Results

Deliverables

1. **Description of concept**, functional design and technical consideration for implementing the idea. These results have been documented in the prototype design document available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320815>. In this document the various functionalities, design considerations as well as future developments are presented.
2. **A prototype platform** that connects the different ideas, possibilities and perspectives with the current COVID-19 situation. The source code is available via Github (see links at the end of the document). A demo version is available via: <http://dev.watmagweltijdenscrisis.nl/>. This prototype is used for evaluation purposes and uncovering various design considerations.
3. **Integration** in (the network of) Safety Region Rotterdam-Rijnmond. Integrating the concept as an additional service atop the current crisis communication. Additionally involving civic organizations, communities and other stakeholders to contribute ideas and disseminate the platform.

Impact & Risks

(under development) These effects may occur, if the above mentioned results are achieved or during the process of achieving the goals and results.

	Positive	Negative
Unintentionally	It might increase trust in governmental institutions on the long term	1) It might not be in line with the traditional way of governmental communication, which could be confusing for Dutch civilians 2) It might inspire civilians to slip through, or find loopholes of the COVID-19 agreements
Intentionally	1) Increase civilians willingness to follow the COVID-19 rules 2) Give civilians activity-inspiration during the COVID-19 crisis 3) Motivate civilians to stay positive and open towards creativity during the COVID-19 crisis	x

Therefore, this platform is not a:

- Replacement of the current crisis communication channels of any government agency
- Blog or any kind of forum that (until now) serves a commercial point of view
- Is (until further notice) focused on the COVID-19 crisis

Next steps & Future developments

There are various directions for the further development of this concept and the related prototype. In the next stage the partner in this project aims to invite other partners in the region Rotterdam-Rijnmond to help the development on both a technical level (for the platform) as well as for communication (content and dissemination). At the same time the aim is to share the concept and insights gained with the wider crisis management community to facilitate the discussion about an additional, supportive, narrative linked to the information needs of the population.

Community & Ecosystem

At the moment the platform provides an overview of ideas entered which is filtered based on choices made by the user. While some specific development suggestions (mainly functionalities) have been listed in the design document (see below), the next step in the developments seem to move towards an interactive platform. Specifically a platform where ideas (information provided) and the need to find alternatives (information needs) are being matched. Subsequently better understand and match these information offers and needs.

Technical possibilities exist to determine what alternatives users are looking for and which ideas resonate with their needs (actively through voting or commenting, or passively through tracking the user in the app). Unaddressed needs could be identified and offered as a 'challenge' for groups to develop ideas for. At the same time this also shows any gaps in the current coverage of (viable) alternatives. Vice versa, ideas could be added on the platform by various communities and actively shared with users based on their profile (again either actively created on the platform, or imported from social media profiles).

While these developments come with important caveats around security and privacy, technical possibilities exist to identify the information needs of the users and offer a platform to share creative ideas. The possibilities allow this matching to be actively managed through the platform.

Development

The partners provided the concept design and description for the prototype. The prototype provides solutions and a blueprint that enables the execution of this concept into reality. As for further development, the VR-RR is not responsible for execution. If any partner of the prototype wishes to execute the idea, new arrangements are necessary including all responsibilities and tasks. As for new partners who are interested and/or want to further develop this prototype, new arrangements with the partners from the prototype are necessary as well.

Dissemination

It can be envisioned that in the future there will be multiple applications offering this functionality and service to the public. Different regions, sectors, cultures and focus groups could have their own app tailored to their needs. While a central directory would provide the users with the most ideas, this can also be overwhelming and hard to manage or moderate. Therefore the ideas presented and concepts presented here mainly serve to determine the feasibility and a possible technical realization. The exact design, implementation and governance of the concept and platform are to be developed in close collaboration with the stakeholders.

Most importantly the concept and prototype introduced in this report are meant to increase the awareness of and facilitate the discussion around the provision of tailored information. The concept note and prototype are freely available for other organizations to use under the CC BY-SA (documents) and the GNU GPL V3 license (code). These documents can be found under the following links and public repositories:

- Concept note: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320815>
- Prototype design: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320815>
- Online demo: <https://dev.watmagweltijdenscrisis.nl/>
- Source code: <https://github.com/kmeesters/COVID-empowered>

Research

Tilburg University and the Safety Region Rotterdam-Rijnmond aim to continue exploring the presented concept and develop additional insights through joint development and research activities. We welcome additional insights, comments and feedback from other interested parties in the development, adoption and research of the concept note. We welcome collaborations on the presented topics and developments and hope that you will support the open development and research.

Use of this concept and documents

This document is publicly available and covered under the CC-BY 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>) . You are free to share this material in any medium or format. You can also adapt or build on the ideas provided here, even commercially. Provided that you give appropriate credit to the authors in your project: Nikki van Emmerloot, Nicole van Batenburg, Kenny Meesters. If you like to know more [contact us!](#)

In short this means that:

You are free to:

- Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format
- Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material

Under the following terms:

- Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
- ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
- No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

This is a human-readable summary of (and not a substitute for) the license which can be found here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode>